

Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19

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Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections, USA**

Authors: Gori Fabio, University of Rome Tor Vergata

ORCID 0000-0002-3927-2834

I have updated the COVID19 infections data and forecast in USA on May 20th, publishing the graphs on the following free blog:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://usacovid19.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here.

The forecast of the total positive cases, according to the Verhulst equation, is over 1,650,000 cases, while the forecast of the total deaths is over 90,000.

The forecast of the new cases and deaths are showing the trend to decrease.